

Prevalence of Left Ventricular Diastolic Dysfunction in Patients with Subclinical Hypothyroidism

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Abstract:

Background: Subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) is a common endocrine condition marked by normal amounts of free thyroxine (T4) but high levels of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). There is growing evidence that left ventricular diastolic dysfunction (LVDD), a disease linked to higher rates of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality, may be facilitated by SCH. This investigation sought to determine the prevalence of LVDD in SCH patients as well as the clinical and biochemical variables linked to the condition.

Methods: A total of 130 participants diagnosed with SCH were included. Data on baseline characteristics, biochemical parameters, and echocardiographic assessments were collected. The prevalence of LVDD was determined, and logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent predictors of LVDD.

Results: The population consisted of 86 females (66.2%) and 44 males (33.8%) with a mean age of 45.3 ± 12.7 years. LVDD was identified in 52 participants, yielding a prevalence of 40.0%. Participants with LVDD were older and had higher BMI, systolic blood pressure, TSH levels, total cholesterol, and triglycerides compared to those without LVDD. Logistic regression analysis revealed that age, BMI, systolic blood pressure, TSH levels, and total cholesterol were significant independent predictors of LVDD.

Conclusion: According to the study, LVDD is highly prevalent in individuals with SCH and is significantly correlated with age, BMI, systolic blood pressure, TSH, and total cholesterol. These results emphasise the necessity of routine cardiovascular monitoring in SCH patients in order to identify and treat any possible diastolic dysfunction in a timely manner.

Recommendations: Routine cardiovascular assessments should be considered for patients with SCH, particularly those with higher BMI, elevated TSH levels, and unfavorable lipid profiles. Further studies are warranted to explore the benefits of early intervention and management strategies in this population.

Keywords: Subclinical Hypothyroidism, Left Ventricular Diastolic Dysfunction, Prevalence, Cardiovascular Risk Factors, TSH Levels.

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Introduction

An endocrine condition known as subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) is typified by normal amounts of free thyroxine (T4) but high serum levels of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). Even while hypothyroidism is not always evident in SCH patients, this illness is becoming more and more known for its ability to negatively impact several organ systems, most notably the cardiovascular system [1].

An inadequate diastolic filling of the left ventricle results in elevated filling pressures and a possible progression to heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF). This condition is known as left ventricular diastolic dysfunction (LVDD). LVDD is linked to unfavourable cardiovascular outcomes, such as elevated morbidity and mortality, and is an

early indicator of cardiac dysfunction [2]. According to new research, SCH may have a role in the onset and development of LVDD via a number of pathways, including systemic inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, and changes in the structure and function of the heart.

Numerous research investigations have documented a correlation between SCH and a range of cardiovascular risk factors, such as elevated arterial stiffness, dyslipidaemia, and hypertension [3]. These elements are known to play a role in the pathophysiology of LVDD, indicating a potential connection between diastolic dysfunction and SCH. Research is still being done to determine the precise prevalence of LVDD in SCH patients as well as the underlying processes.

A substantial prevalence of LVDD was found in patients with SCH, according to a recent meta-analysis, underscoring the necessity of more research to fully understand this link [4]. Additionally, considering the possibility of HFpEF development and other unfavourable cardiovascular events, the clinical implications of LVDD in SCH patients are extremely significant. Further research is necessary since, despite the increasing amount of data, opinions regarding the management and screening approaches for LVDD in patients with SCH remain divided [5].

The significance of researching SCH's connection to LVDD is highlighted by the increasing awareness of its influence on cardiovascular health. In order to prevent negative outcomes, it is critical to identify patients who are at risk and adopt appropriate treatment interventions as research continues to unravel the complexity of this association.

The study was conducted to investigate the prevalence of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study took place, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, a tertiary care hospital, between January 2016 and December 2016.

Participants: The study included 130 participants diagnosed with subclinical hypothyroidism. Participants were recruited from the outpatient department of endocrinology.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18-65 years.
- Diagnosed with subclinical hypothyroidism (TSH levels between 4.5-10 mIU/L with normal free T4 levels).
- No prior history of thyroid hormone replacement therapy.

Exclusion Criteria

- History of overt hypothyroidism or hyperthyroidism.
- Presence of any known cardiovascular disease.
- Diabetes mellitus.
- Chronic kidney disease.

- Use of medications affecting thyroid function or cardiovascular system.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected using a computerized randomization method. Information bias was reduced by ensuring that the echocardiographic assessments were performed by a single experienced cardiologist blinded to the participants' thyroid status.

Variables: The primary variable was the presence of LVDD, assessed via echocardiography. Secondary variables included age, sex, BMI, blood pressure, serum TSH, free T4 levels, and lipid profile.

Data Collection: A standardised questionnaire and a review of medical records were used to gather data. Recorded were baseline attributes such as age, sex, BMI, and medical history. To evaluate serum TSH, free T4, and lipid profile, blood samples were taken. To evaluate left ventricular diastolic function, echocardiograms were done.

Procedure: Blood was drawn from the participants after they received a thorough clinical evaluation. Chemiluminescence immunoassay was used to measure the levels of free T4 and serum TSH. The American Society of Echocardiography's standards for performing echocardiographic tests were followed in order to assess left ventricular diastolic performance. E/A ratio, E/e' ratio, and left atrial volume index are among the accepted parameters used to define the existence of diastolic dysfunction.

Statistical Analysis: Version 25 of the SPSS software was used to analyse the data. The study population's baseline characteristics were compiled using descriptive statistics. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05. To find independent determinants of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction, logistic regression analysis was used.

Result

There were 130 participants in the study who had subclinical hypothyroidism; 86 of them were female (66.2%) and 44 were male (33.8%). The participants' average age was 45.3 ± 12.7 years. The baseline characteristics of the research population are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Mean $\pm$ SD / n (%)
Age (years)	45.3 $\pm$ 12.7
Female	86 (66.2)
Male	44 (33.8)
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.8 $\pm$ 4.1
Systolic BP (mmHg)	128.4 $\pm$ 15.2
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	82.6 $\pm$ 9.7
TSH (mIU/L)	6.3 $\pm$ 1.4
Free T4 (pmol/L)	14.6 $\pm$ 1.9
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	212.3 $\pm$ 35.4
LDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	132.8 $\pm$ 28.5
HDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	45.7 $\pm$ 9.2
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	168.5 $\pm$ 40.6

LVDD was identified in 52 out of 130 participants, yielding a prevalence of 40.0%. Table 2 shows the prevalence of DD stratified by gender.

Table 2: Prevalence of Left Ventricular Diastolic Dysfunction by Gender

Gender	Diastolic Dysfunction	No Diastolic Dysfunction	Total
Female	35 (40.7%)	51 (59.3%)	86
Male	17 (38.6%)	27 (61.4%)	44
Total	52 (40.0%)	78 (60.0%)	130

The prevalence of DD did not differ statistically significantly between males and females ($p = 0.79$). The baseline features of individuals with and without LVDD are contrasted in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparison of Characteristics Between Groups

Characteristic	Diastolic Dysfunction (n = 52)	No Diastolic Dysfunction (n = 78)	p-value
Age (years)	48.1 $\pm$ 11.3	43.5 $\pm$ 13.2	0.03
Female	35 (67.3%)	51 (65.4%)	0.82
Male	17 (32.7%)	27 (34.6%)	0.82
BMI (kg/m ²)	29.1 $\pm$ 4.3	27.0 $\pm$ 3.9	0.01
Systolic BP (mmHg)	132.7 $\pm$ 14.8	125.7 $\pm$ 14.9	0.01
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	85.2 $\pm$ 9.1	80.9 $\pm$ 9.7	0.02
TSH (mIU/L)	6.8 $\pm$ 1.3	6.0 $\pm$ 1.4	<0.01
Free T4 (pmol/L)	14.2 $\pm$ 1.8	14.9 $\pm$ 1.9	0.03
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	225.3 $\pm$ 37.1	203.2 $\pm$ 32.5	<0.01
LDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	142.6 $\pm$ 27.4	126.1 $\pm$ 27.9	<0.01
HDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	43.9 $\pm$ 8.7	46.8 $\pm$ 9.4	0.04
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	178.6 $\pm$ 39.1	161.2 $\pm$ 39.7	0.02

Compared to those without diastolic dysfunction, those with diastolic dysfunction were older, had lower levels of free T4 and HDL cholesterol, and higher levels of triglycerides, blood pressure, TSH,

total and LDL cholesterol, and BMI. There are independent factors of LVDD found by logistic regression analysis. Table 4 presents the findings.

Table 4: Logistic Regression Analysis of Predictors for LVDD

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Age (years)	1.05	1.01 - 1.09	0.02
BMI (kg/m ²)	1.10	1.02 - 1.19	0.01
Systolic BP (mmHg)	1.03	1.01 - 1.06	0.01
TSH (mIU/L)	1.45	1.14 - 1.85	<0.01
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	1.02	1.01 - 1.03	<0.01
HDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	0.95	0.91 - 0.99	0.02

Age, BMI, systolic blood pressure, TSH levels, total cholesterol, and HDL cholesterol were significant independent predictors of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction.

Discussion

Thirty-one persons with SCH were included in the study; 66.2 percent of the participants were female. The participants' average age was 45.3 years. 40.0% of the patients were found to have left

ventricular diastolic dysfunction, a high percentage. This high frequency suggests a strong correlation between subclinical hypothyroidism and impaired heart function.

Compared to individuals without diastolic dysfunction, those with dysfunction were older, had higher blood pressure, and a higher BMI. In addition, they showed decreased levels of free T4 and HDL cholesterol and increased levels of triglycerides, total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, and TSH. These variations show that people who have diastolic dysfunction typically have a worse cardiovascular risk profile, which may be a factor in their compromised heart performance.

A number of independent predictors of LVDD were found using logistic regression analysis. These predictors included age, BMI, SBP, TSH levels, total cholesterol, and HDL cholesterol. To be more precise, the likelihood of developing diastolic dysfunction rose by 5% with every year that an individual aged. Similarly, the probabilities increased by 10% and 45%, respectively, with each unit increase in BMI and TSH levels. While higher HDL cholesterol seemed to be protective, higher SBP and total cholesterol also markedly raised the risk.

The results imply that routine cardiovascular monitoring may be necessary in people with subclinical hypothyroidism in order to identify early indicators of diastolic dysfunction. This might make it possible to manage and reduce cardiovascular risks through prompt actions. In addition, managing variables including blood pressure, cholesterol, and BMI may help lower the chance of LVDD in this group of patients.

SCH and subclinical left cardiac dysfunction were studied in 1,078 patients using two-dimensional speckle-tracking echocardiography. Despite having a normal LV ejection fraction, it was discovered that those with SCH had significantly impaired left atrial (LA) reservoir and conduit strain, which are markers of subclinical left heart disease. The study emphasises how critical it is to identify cardiac dysfunction in SCH patients as soon as possible [6].

A study used the left ventricular global longitudinal strain (LVGLS) and myocardial performance index (MPI) to evaluate 105 patients with SCH. MPI, conventional, and tissue-Doppler imaging (TDI) characteristics revealed a greater incidence of subclinical left ventricular dysfunction (LVD) in SCH patients with presystolic wave (PSW). In patients with SCH, the existence of PSW was an independent predictor of subclinical LVD [7].

A case-control study including 36 SCH patients and 36 euthyroid controls was carried out at a tertiary care centre in South India. Compared to

30.5% of controls, the study revealed that 72.2% of SCH patients had some type of LVDD. In patients with schizophrenia, parameters including the septal E/e' ratio and isovolumetric relaxation time were significantly higher [8].

A case-control research with ninety-five participants revealed that LVDD is common in patients with SCH. Between SCH patients and controls, notable variations were noted in measures such as E wave velocity, E/A ratio, and isovolumic relaxation duration. TSH levels and markers of LV diastolic dysfunction were found to be strongly positively correlated in SCH patients [9].

Forty SCH patients participated in a randomised clinical trial to evaluate the impact of levothyroxine medication on diastolic dysfunction. After one year of levothyroxine treatment, the study demonstrated significant improvements in echocardiographic parameters such as MV.E, MV.A, and E/A ratio, indicating that diastolic dysfunction in SCH may be reversible with the right medication [10].

Conclusion

The study demonstrated a high prevalence (40.0%) of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism. Key predictors of diastolic dysfunction included age, BMI, systolic blood pressure, TSH levels, total cholesterol, and HDL cholesterol. These findings underscore the importance of cardiovascular assessment in patients with subclinical hypothyroidism to identify and manage potential diastolic dysfunction.

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